

USE OF INNOVATIVE AND INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE SYSTEM OF ECONOMIC EDUCATION

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Annotation: *This article discusses the use of innovative and information technologies in the economic education system, including innovative forms and methods of teaching and modern information and communication technologies, the effective use of innovative, pedagogical and digital technologies in the education system and its widespread application.*

Keywords: *Educational ceremonies, scientific educational institutions, economic education, innovation, information and communication technologies, digital technologies, distance learning, e-learning.*

Nowadays, due to innovations and the rapid development of information and communication technologies, their use in all spheres of socio-economic life, especially in education, is becoming the most pressing task of our century.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" supports innovative activities in educational institutions and the implementation of curricula with the use of innovative technologies, the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities of students in accordance with distance learning curricula and training programs. Important tasks such as distance learning using the network, the use of modern pedagogical technologies, innovative forms and methods of teaching and information and communication technologies in the implementation of curricula and study programs, the effective use of new foreign pedagogical technologies and its positive experience in the education system.

In addition, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the Strategy" Digital Uzbekistan - 2030 "and measures for its effective implementation" will improve the e-government system, further develop the local market of software and information technology. develops, the organization of IT parks in all regions. as well as the provision of qualified personnel for the industry, the organization of training and retraining of responsible heads of government agencies and organizations, local executive authorities on the basis of specialized universities and training centers for digital technologies.

In this regard, the training of qualified personnel in higher education institutions of the country, increasing the effectiveness of education, ensuring the training of highly qualified personnel, creating opportunities for independent learning and self-

government, developing students' creative abilities, independent access to information Learning to use a variety of methods, save time on teaching materials, manage education and automate comprehensive analysis using modern information and communication technologies, further develop e-resources and distance learning systems, popularize IT professions among students. important tasks. Information technology is widely used in its implementation. In this regard, the Action Strategy for Education Reform and a number of normative documents further improve the system of continuing education, increase the capacity of quality educational services, continue the policy of training highly qualified personnel in accordance with modern needs of the labor market, the need to stimulate research and innovation, create effective implementation mechanisms, establish specialized research and experimental laboratories, high-tech centers and technoparks in universities and research institutes.

In accordance with this, the existing ministries and departments, public associations are carrying out important tasks aimed at the development of innovation and information and communication technologies in education.

We know that pedagogical activity is based on research, creative work and aspiration. Innovations in the educational process, advanced pedagogical technologies, innovations, traditional and non-traditional methods of teaching do not enter education on their own. In this regard, the relevant ministries, departments, banking and financial organizations, small and medium enterprises in all sectors of the national economy, including private and joint ventures, farms, as well as scientific institutions of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, universities, research centers, International conferences, scientific-practical seminars and innovation fairs are held with the participation of experimental and design organizations, as well as representatives of international organizations.

As a result, the effectiveness of innovative activities of our specialists is growing, mutually beneficial links between science and industry are strengthening, as well as the regular use of innovative educational technologies and information and communication resources in the training process of higher education, highly qualified professionals. In order to implement and develop, "Innovation Center", "Digital Technology Center", "IT Center" and "IT Parks" are being established. This is one of the foundations for creating the most sustainable - innovative and digital economy in the context of globalization. In this regard, the Action Strategy is aimed at improving the quality and efficiency of higher education institutions through the introduction of information and communication technologies in the economy, social sphere and management, the development of education and science, the introduction of international standards of quality assessment. education and upbringing. important tasks such as stimulating innovative activity, creating effective mechanisms for the application of scientific and innovative achievements in practice. Innovative development of the economy, including the system of economic education, will be an important factor in overcoming the impact

of the pandemic on the economy of our country quickly and cheaply, its further development, increasing competitiveness and prestige in world economic relations.

In general, the economic literacy, knowledge, level, and quality of the population, as well as the compliance of the education system with market requirements are key factors of an economically developed state. At present, the literacy of the population, including the share of highly educated personnel and the widespread use of information and communication technologies among the population, plays an important role in the development of the country's economy. An urgent task is to analyze the measures taken to reform the higher education system and the measures being developed to address the global challenges facing it, as well as the problems that need to be addressed. The main problems of all educational institutions are the introduction of modern management in education, the use of advanced methods of financing, improving the quality of education, improving the material and technical base of educational institutions at the expense of modern students. technological equipment. The country's higher education system mainly teaches young people the existing norms of life in society, fosters a high level of spiritual maturity, forms highly qualified modern professionals and provides equal access to knowledge, interests and aspirations of different segments of society.

Creating conditions for the harmonious development and upbringing of the younger generation has been a priority of state policy in the interests of young people since the early years of independence of Uzbekistan. After all, this is a future-oriented investment.

Today, the share of young people seeking higher education is growing day by day. If in 2017 the number of students studying in higher education institutions of the country was 314,465 people, in 2018 this figure increased to 373,473 people, and in 2019 the number of students studying in more than 110 universities of the country Exceeded 468,399 people. If we look at the dynamics of changes in the coverage of young people with higher education, in 2017 it was 9 percent, in 2018 this figure rose to 15 percent and in 2019 to 20 percent. Achieving 50 percent coverage of young people with higher education by 2030 is one of the key challenges facing the higher education system.

These figures show that the demand for education in our country, especially in higher education, is growing every year. So, the thinking and consciousness of today's youth is growing. They realized that in order to become a person needed by society in the future, they had to find their place among the cadres who met the requirements of the time. The next generation must have the ability to work with constantly evolving technologies, work in production with a good knowledge of marketing and management activities, create innovation.

Among the rapidly growing needs of our society for the introduction of information and communication technologies in the educational process in higher education are electronic textbooks and manuals, virtual stands, intelligent systems, information and communication technologies. and distance learning, in addition to distance learning. At

the same time, the high level of development of information and communication technologies in Uzbekistan also means that there are sufficient conditions for the implementation of distance learning. The growing number of Internet services, the need for their correct and effective use in the educational process requires the gradual introduction of the national strategy of information and communication technologies in the education system of the country.

This strategy includes such processes as improving the quality of socio-economic education through the provision of higher education institutions with information and communication technologies, the creation of e-learning programs, improving the knowledge and skills of teachers and students in the use of information technology. Extensive use of information and communication and digital technologies in the classroom increases the effectiveness of the reception and mastering of educational materials by students. The development of information and communication and digital technologies in the economic education system involves several stages. The goal of each phase is to effectively apply these technologies in higher education.

The first stage is mainly the collection of logistics, software, organizational and other necessary resources. The end of this phase can be seen in the low cost of using the Internet and the creation of personal information resources (electronic textbooks and libraries) when it is used as an additional source of information in the learning process. experience in the widespread application of distance learning in all departments.

In the second stage, planning is made to use mainly created information resources and digital technologies in the distance learning process. This stage ends when the higher education institution holds scientific and practical conferences and seminars on distance learning and the widespread use of information and communication and digital technologies, as well as leadership in the creation of systems and kits for distance learning.

And finally, the final stage is economic information education. At the end of this stage, traditional and distance learning methods will be introduced in higher education institutions through the use of modern information and communication and digital technologies in all specialties, an electronic management system will be created, cooperation with local and foreign educational institutions will be established. 'continuous connections are established. to be established. adequate performance of electronic libraries is ensured.

It should be noted that while education has a special role in the economic sphere of society, educational activity is an important part of the economic development of society. Therefore, by informing the process of economic education, it is possible to develop the intellectual potential and creative abilities of the individual, increase the economic knowledge and skills of every citizen in society, create conditions for accelerated education. Today, not only in the field of education, but in all sectors of the national economy, innovative technologies, Internet, e-commerce, e-business, virtual

commerce, online business, blockchain, artificial intelligence, widespread use of virtual education, distance learning and virtual stand technology is a requirement of the time to achieve computer literacy of young people and professionals in the production of software products at the national level. The availability of opportunities for improving and innovative development of the education system in our country is reflected in the following:

- First, the higher education system and scientific institutions in the country are the main place for scientific research and studies;

- Second, the scientific and pedagogical staff has the potential to create and implement innovative ideas in higher education;

- Third, there is an opportunity to study the experience of foreign countries on innovations in the education system and their implementation in the local context.

In this regard, for the development of innovative activities in higher education institutions operating in the field of economics, it is expedient to pay special attention to the following.

- each educational institution to study the situation in the domestic and foreign markets of its services, conduct large-scale marketing research and on this basis to develop short and long-term plans, strategies and roadmaps for innovation in economic and pedagogical processes and services;

- Wide introduction of modern educational, innovative and digital technologies that provide training of highly qualified personnel competitive in domestic and foreign markets for economic education services;

- Attracting direct investments of local and foreign investors in order to introduce high-efficiency modern information and innovative technologies in the education system, to ensure the expansion of the educational institution's participation in local and international competitions and projects;

- The organization of training, retraining and advanced training of specialists in accordance with the innovative and information and communication technologies used in the educational institution;

- assistance in the promotion of innovations in the education system, including through the introduction of modern, interactive and creative teaching methods, ensuring the development of innovative curricula that provide for the widespread use of digital technologies;

- formation of a modern management system that ensures the effectiveness of innovative processes in the management of the education system.

These ideas will not only ensure the sustainable economic growth of the educational institution, but also increase its competitiveness in the international arena.

In conclusion, our main task is to analyze the current state and future prospects of the implementation of the National Strategy for Innovation and Information and Communication Technologies in the economic education system of our country, the

study and implementation of e-learning and telecommunications opportunities. Indeed, the science of Uzbekistan has a great reputation around the world, and its practical achievements with innovative features are in great demand in the international technology market. As innovation and information and communication technologies penetrate into all spheres of public life, it will undoubtedly ensure the socio-economic and cultural development of the state and remain the main driving force of the development of our century.

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